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INFLUENCE OF WATCHING K-DRAMA WITH ENGLISH SUBTITLES ON VOCABULARY ACQUISITION AMONG THE BSED ENGLISH STUDENTS AT SNSU CLAVER CAMPUS

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Abstract

This study explored the relationship between K-Drama viewing habits and English vocabulary acquisition among BSED-English students, specifically examining whether a significant correlation exists between these variables.

Using a quantitative descriptive–correlational design, data were collected from 131 students through a survey on viewing habits and subtitle attention, along with a 30-item vocabulary test. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and Pearson Product–Moment Correlation.

Findings showed that most students watch K-Dramas occasionally and for less than an hour, while generally paying attention to English subtitles and perceiving them as helpful for vocabulary learning. Vocabulary test results indicated satisfactory knowledge, and a significant relationship was found between viewing habits, particularly subtitle attention, and vocabulary acquisition, supporting the use of subtitled media as a supplementary learning tool.

Keyword: K-Dramas, Media, Subtitles, Vocabulary, Acquisition

INTRODUCTION

Vocabulary is essential for effective communication, comprehension, and expression in English, particularly for BSED-English students whose academic success and future teaching roles depend on strong lexical competence. A well-developed vocabulary enables learners to understand texts, convey ideas clearly, and function effectively in various communicative contexts (Hsu, 2023; Rosales, 2019).

In the digital age, students are increasingly exposed to multimedia platforms such as K-Dramas, which are widely popular and accessible. Watching these dramas with English subtitles provides learners with opportunities to encounter vocabulary in authentic contexts, potentially supporting incidental vocabulary acquisition through repeated exposure to dialogue and text (Alejandro et al., 2023; Rinekso et al., 2021).

K-Dramas with subtitles promote incidental learning by combining visual and auditory elements that reinforce comprehension and retention. This multimodal approach connects words to context, emotions, and expressions, making vocabulary learning more engaging and less pressured compared to traditional methods, while encouraging active language use (Masduqi & Khairunnisa, 2024; Paivio, 1986; Rinekso et al.).

The growing popularity of subtitled K-Dramas suggests their potential as educational tools. Integrating such entertainment-based materials into language learning may offer more engaging and effective strategies for vocabulary development beyond the classroom (Alejado et al., 2023; Hsu, 2023; Miranda & Estoque, 2023).

Despite existing international studies highlighting the benefits of subtitled media, most focus on learners' perceptions rather than measurable outcomes. In the Philippine context, particularly at SNSU-Claver Campus, there is a lack of empirical research examining the relationship between K-Drama viewing habits, subtitle attention, and actual vocabulary acquisition, underscoring the need for further investigation.

Asio (2022) found that increased screen time among students, especially during the pandemic, affects learning behaviors, motivation, and language exposure, which may contribute to vocabulary acquisition (Asio, 2022; Lukram et al., 2026). Theoretical foundations on incidental vocabulary learning emphasize that learners acquire new words through repeated exposure in meaningful contexts. Nation (2001) and Webb

(2019) explain that engagement and contextual understanding are essential, while Dang, Lu, and Webb (2021) demonstrated that both single words and collocations can be learned incidentally through frequent exposure.

Furthermore, studies on multimodal input suggest that combining visual and auditory elements enhances comprehension and retention, although vocabulary gains require repeated and varied exposure (Webb et al., 2023). In this context, K-Dramas with English subtitles serve as an effective medium for incidental learning. Research by Masduqi and Khairunnisa (2024), Nurhayati (2022), Putra (2023), and Rinekso et al. (2021) consistently shows that subtitles improve word recognition, retention, and motivation, while Philippine-based studies confirm that learners benefit from meaningful and engaging exposure to vocabulary (Alejado et al., 2023).

Overall, the literature supports the idea that watching K-Dramas with English subtitles can enhance vocabulary acquisition in an engaging and motivating way. However, most studies focus on learners' perceptions rather than measurable outcomes, highlighting the need for further research to examine the direct impact of K-Drama viewing habits on actual vocabulary development.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This study aims to determine the influence of watching Korean dramas (K-Dramas) with English subtitles on the English vocabulary acquisition of BSED English students at Surigao del Norte State University, Claver Campus. Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What are the watching habits of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Frequency of watching K-Dramas
 - 1.2 Number of hours spending watching K-Dramas
2. What is the level of the respondents' attention to English subtitles while watching K-Dramas?
3. What is the level of English vocabulary acquisition of the respondents as reflected in their exposure to English-subtitled K-Dramas in terms of:
 - 2.1 Self-perceived vocabulary development
 - 2.2 Actual vocabulary performance
4. Is there a significant relationship between K-Drama viewing habits, including frequency of watching and attention to subtitles, and their level of English vocabulary acquisition?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design The study employed a descriptive–correlational research design to examine the relationship between K-Drama viewing habits, specifically frequency, viewing duration, and attention to English subtitles, and the English vocabulary acquisition of BSED

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English students at Surigao del Norte State University Claver Campus. It is descriptive in that it presents and summarizes existing conditions using statistical tools such as frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation, and item analysis, and correlational in that it determines the relationship between variables without manipulation. To assess the degree of association between K-Drama viewing habits (independent variable) and vocabulary acquisition (dependent variable), inferential statistics, including Pearson Product-Moment Correlation and Chi-square test, were utilized, allowing the researchers to derive meaningful insights for academic improvement.

Respondents This study involved a sample of 131 BSEd-English students from Surigao del Norte State University, Claver Extension Campus. The respondents were chosen because they are English major students who are exposed to various media, including K-Dramas with English subtitles. Participants are selected based on specific characteristics relevant to the research objectives (Palinkas et al., 2015). This approach was appropriate as the study focused on BSED English students who watch K-Dramas with English subtitles, ensuring that the selected respondents could provide relevant and meaningful data for examining the relationship between viewing habits and English vocabulary acquisition.

Research Environment The study was conducted at Surigao del Norte State University (SNSU) Claver Campus in Bagakay, Claver, Surigao del Norte, Philippines. SNSU, originally established in 1969 and granted university status in 2022, is a public higher education institution with multiple campuses aimed at expanding access to tertiary education. The Claver Campus offers various undergraduate programs, including BSED English, and provides both formal instruction and opportunities for informal language exposure, making it an appropriate setting for examining the relationship between K-Drama viewing habits and English vocabulary acquisition.

Ethics and Data Gathering Procedure Before conducting the study, the researchers sought permission from the Campus Director of SNSU-Claver and the subject adviser of the BSEd-English students. After approval, the researchers distributed the research questionnaires through Google Forms. A short orientation was conducted to explain the purpose of the study and clarify the items in the questionnaire. Respondents were assured that their participation was voluntary, and that all information would be treated with confidentiality. After the questionnaires were answered, the researchers collected the data immediately after the set deadline. The gathered responses were then tallied, analyzed, and interpreted according to the study's objectives.

Data Analysis The gathered data were analyzed using several statistical tools. Frequency count and percentage were used to describe the respondents' K-Drama viewing habits, including how often they watch and the number of hours they spend watching. Mean and standard deviation were utilized to determine the respondents' level of agreement regarding their attention to English subtitles and their self-perceived vocabulary development. Item analysis was conducted to assess the respondents' actual vocabulary performance by determining the number of correct and incorrect responses for each item, calculating the success rate, and classifying items according to their level of difficulty. Furthermore, the Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) was employed to determine whether a significant relationship exists between the frequency of watching K-Dramas with English subtitles and the respondents' level of English vocabulary acquisition.

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1. Frequency of Watching Habits The findings revealed that the respondents generally have limited exposure to K-Dramas. Most students reported watching K-Dramas rarely (29.77%) or not at all (20.61%), while only a small proportion indicated daily viewing (11.45%). Similarly, the majority of respondents spend less than one hour watching K-Dramas (36.64%), suggesting minimal engagement with this form of entertainment. These results may be attributed to academic commitments and other responsibilities that limit students' leisure time.

According to Asio (2022) and Rinekso et al. (2021), students often prioritize academic tasks over recreational media consumption. Despite the limited viewing frequency and duration, Webb (2019) emphasized that even brief exposure to subtitled audiovisual content can facilitate incidental vocabulary acquisition, particularly when learners actively engage with the language presented in subtitles.

2. Attention to English Subtitles While Watching K-Dramas The respondents demonstrated a generally high level of attention to English subtitles, as reflected by the overall mean of 3.9, interpreted as "Agree." The highest-rated behavior was paying close attention to subtitles to understand the storyline, indicating that subtitles serve as an important aid in comprehension. Respondents also reported noticing unfamiliar words, replaying scenes, and relying on subtitles to understand character interactions.

These findings support Peters and Webb (2020), who found that subtitle exposure improves both comprehension and vocabulary learning. Likewise, Teng (2021) argued that learners acquire vocabulary more effectively when they focus on meaning during subtitle viewing. The results further align with Montero Perez, Peters, and Desmet (2021) and Lee (2022), who highlighted the value of combining textual, visual, and auditory information in supporting language acquisition.

3. Self-Perceived Vocabulary Development The findings indicate that respondents perceive English subtitles as beneficial to their vocabulary development, with an overall mean of 3.9. Students agreed that subtitles help them learn new words, understand meanings more clearly, recall previously encountered vocabulary, and apply newly learned terms in communication.

These results suggest that subtitles provide meaningful contextual exposure that promotes vocabulary growth. Reynolds et al. (2022) found that captioned and subtitled videos enhance vocabulary acquisition by strengthening learners' understanding of word forms and meanings. Similarly, Teng (2022) and Teng (2023) emphasized that audiovisual materials facilitate incidental vocabulary learning through repeated contextual exposure. However, respondents also acknowledged difficulties in remembering some vocabulary items and applying them in academic settings, indicating that exposure alone may not guarantee long-term retention. This observation supports Reynolds et al. (2022), who stressed the importance of reinforcement and active language use in sustaining vocabulary gains.

4. Vocabulary Test Performance The vocabulary assessment results demonstrated generally strong performance among the respondents, as evidenced by the high success rates recorded across most test items. Items Q7 and Q2 obtained the highest success rates, indicating that these vocabulary concepts were familiar to the respondents. The majority of the items fell within the easy to moderately difficult categories, suggesting that students possessed adequate vocabulary knowledge in the tested areas. According to Gierl and Haladyna (2020), items with high success rates often reflect mastery of fundamental concepts and provide evidence of learner competence.

Meanwhile, Brookhart and Nitko (2019) emphasized that a balanced assessment should include items of varying difficulty levels to ensure accurate measurement of learners' abilities. The relatively low performance on Item Q25 may indicate the presence of more complex vocabulary or concepts that require further instructional attention, consistent with the observations of Downing and Haladyna (2021).

5. Item Difficulty Analysis The item difficulty analysis revealed that the majority of the test items were classified as easy, while a smaller number were moderately difficult and only one item was categorized as difficult.

This distribution suggests that the test was generally appropriate for the respondents' proficiency level while still providing opportunities to distinguish varying levels of vocabulary knowledge. Karelia et al. (2024) emphasized that assessments containing a balanced range of item difficulties contribute to more accurate evaluation and stronger measurement reliability. The presence of moderately difficult and difficult items also ensures that the assessment can identify areas where students may require additional support or instruction.

6. Relationship Between K-Drama Viewing Habits and Vocabulary Acquisition The Chi-square analysis revealed a significant relationship between the frequency of watching K-Dramas and vocabulary acquisition. This finding suggests that students who watch K-Dramas more frequently tend to possess higher levels of English vocabulary knowledge. Teng (2022) explained that repeated exposure to captioned audiovisual materials promotes incidental vocabulary acquisition by repeatedly presenting learners with new lexical items in meaningful contexts.

In contrast, the number of hours spent watching K-Dramas did not demonstrate a significant relationship with vocabulary acquisition, indicating that consistency of exposure may be more influential than viewing duration. This supports Teng's (2022) assertion that regular encounters with language input are more beneficial for vocabulary development than prolonged but infrequent exposure.

7. Correlation Between Viewing Habits and Vocabulary Acquisition The correlation analysis revealed a moderate positive relationship between the frequency of watching K-Dramas and vocabulary acquisition, as well as a weak positive relationship between viewing duration and vocabulary acquisition. These findings indicate that students who watch K-Dramas more frequently and for longer periods tend to demonstrate better vocabulary performance.

However, the stronger correlation observed for viewing frequency suggests that regular exposure may be a more important factor in vocabulary learning than total viewing time. Teng (2023) highlighted that repeated encounters with vocabulary through captioned audiovisual materials facilitate recognition, comprehension, and retention of new words, ultimately contributing to vocabulary growth.

8. Influence of Subtitle Attention on Vocabulary Acquisition Among the variables examined, attention to English subtitles demonstrated the strongest relationship with vocabulary acquisition. Students who actively engaged with subtitles were more likely to achieve higher vocabulary scores, indicating that subtitle attention plays a crucial role in language learning. Vandergriff and Baker (2021) noted that repeated exposure to subtitled content strengthens learners' ability to form connections between word forms and meanings.

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Similarly, Reynolds et al. (2022) found that subtitles provide visual reinforcement that enhances vocabulary learning and comprehension. The findings suggest that active processing of subtitle content, rather than passive viewing alone, contributes significantly to vocabulary development.

9. Summary of Hypothesis Testing The overall findings confirm that K-Drama viewing habits are significantly associated with English vocabulary acquisition. Frequency of watching K-Dramas, hours spent watching, and attention to English subtitles all demonstrated significant relationships with vocabulary development, although subtitle attention emerged as the strongest predictor.

These results support Teng (2023), Vandergriff and Baker (2021), and Montero (2022), who collectively emphasized the role of repeated exposure, meaningful engagement, and subtitle use in promoting vocabulary acquisition. The rejection of the null hypotheses indicates that K-Drama viewing, particularly when accompanied by active attention to English subtitles, can contribute positively to learners' vocabulary development.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study examined the relationship between K-Drama viewing habits with English subtitles and English vocabulary acquisition among students. The findings revealed that respondents generally have limited exposure to K-Dramas, as most reported watching them infrequently and for relatively short periods. Despite this limited exposure, respondents demonstrated a high level of attention to English subtitles while watching, indicating that subtitles play a significant role in their viewing experience. The results further showed that respondents perceive English subtitles as helpful in learning new vocabulary and understanding word meanings in context. Moreover, the vocabulary assessment indicated that respondents possess a generally satisfactory level of English vocabulary knowledge, as reflected in their high success rates across most test items.

The study also established that K-Drama viewing habits are significantly associated with English vocabulary acquisition. Specifically, the frequency of watching K-Dramas and the level of attention given to English subtitles were found to have significant positive relationships with vocabulary development. Although the number of hours spent watching showed a weaker relationship, it remained a contributing factor to vocabulary growth. These findings suggest that regular exposure to English subtitles, coupled with active engagement in subtitle reading, can support incidental vocabulary learning and contribute to the development of English language proficiency.

Based on these findings, it can be concluded that English subtitles serve as a valuable language-learning resource that supports vocabulary acquisition among students. K-Dramas, when viewed with English subtitles, provide meaningful and contextualized language input that may enhance vocabulary knowledge and comprehension. Therefore, subtitle-assisted viewing can be considered a useful supplementary approach to English language learning.

Recommendations suggest that students are encouraged to watch K-Dramas with English subtitles as a supplementary tool for improving their English vocabulary. By actively paying attention to subtitles, unfamiliar words, and contextual meanings, learners may enhance their vocabulary knowledge and comprehension skills. Regular exposure to subtitle-supported content may also help students become more familiar with the practical use of English in authentic situations.

Teachers and educational institutions may incorporate subtitled audiovisual materials, such as K-Dramas, films, and television programs, into language learning activities. These resources can provide meaningful and contextualized language input that supports vocabulary development while increasing student engagement and motivation. Schools may also promote the use of authentic media resources as supplementary learning materials to strengthen students' language-learning experiences.

Future researchers are encouraged to conduct similar studies using larger and more diverse samples to improve the generalizability of the findings. Further investigations may also examine other language-related variables, such as listening comprehension, speaking proficiency, reading comprehension, and language motivation, to gain a broader understanding of the impact of subtitle-assisted viewing on English language acquisition.

Overall, the study highlights the potential of English-subtitled K-Dramas as an accessible and engaging medium for vocabulary learning. While viewing habits alone may not fully determine language development, active engagement with subtitles can serve as an important factor in enhancing students' vocabulary acquisition and supporting their overall English language proficiency.

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